

CERTAINTY FMI's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for XXXXX data created at the FMI is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for XXX data at FMI is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Funder

European Commission||EC

Grant

CERTAINTY

Researchers

Harri Kokkola (orcid:0000-0002-1404-6670)

Organizations

Finnish Meteorological Institute

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY FMI's DMP](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for XXXXX data created at the FMI is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for XXX data at FMI is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

Researchers:

[Harri Kokkola \(orcid:0000-0002-1404-6670\)](#)

Organizations:

[Finnish Meteorological Institute](#)

Contact: [Anca Hienola](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Input data for UCLALES-SALSA model

Input data required to run simulations of aerosol-cloud-radiation interactions with UCLALES-SALSA model in selected cloud cases

The data for initializing the UCLALES-SALSA model includes:

- Vertical profiles of temperature and humidity
- Surface fluxes of moisture and radiation
- Vertical profiles of aerosol size distributions and composition

Additional vertical profiles of temperature, specific humidity and ozone mixing ratio at constant pressure levels are derived from reanalyzed ECMWF-ERA5 data and used as model input to resolve the atmospheric radiative transfer balance

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: Dataset

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Large-eddy simulations with UCLALES-SALSA require the following input files:

1. **sound_in** : .txt file containing vertical profiles of temperature or potential temperature, specific moisture and horizontal wind components along the vertical model domain. It can be built from:

- 1.1 Radiosonde observations for the specific cloud case to be simulated
- 1.2. ERA 5 reanalyzed data on pressure levels

2. **background_radiation_profile**: .txt file containing vertical profiles of of pressure, air temperature, specific humidity and ozone concentrations. This file can be built using ERA 5 reanalyzed data on pressure levels.

3. **runles**: automatic builder of the namelist file needed to run UCLALES-SALSA. It contains other specific model parameters needed to run simulations with UCLALES-SALSA (e.g. large-scale wind divergence, surface albedo). It must be set up by the modeller according the cloud case. The description of the runles file can be reviewed in

<https://github.com/UCLALES-SALSA/UCLALES-SALSA/blob/master/bin/runles>

3.1 Aerosol size distribution, mixing state and composition can be derived from ground-based observations carried out with Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer

(SMPS) systems, Aerosol Particle Sizer (APS) systems and Aerosol Chemical Speciation Monitors (ACMS).

3.2 Surface fluxes of moisture and energy can be obtained from ERA 5 reanalysis data on single pressure levels.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades.

Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Input files for UCLALES-SALSA are in text format.
ERA5 datasets can be GRIB, NetCDF formats.

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

One simulation requires: 1. sound_in file : 5 Kb 2. background_radiation_profile: 5 Kb 3. runles: 25 Kb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

Each dataset is used to build initial conditions for numerical resolution of mass, motion, energy and radiative transfer equations in the model domain.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023): ERA5 hourly data on pressure levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.bd0915c6 (Accessed on 22-01-2024)

Citing the data:

Hersbach, H., Bell, B., Berrisford, P., Biavati, G., Horányi, A., Muñoz Sabater, J., Nicolas, J., Peubey, C., Radu, R., Rozum, I., Schepers, D., Simmons, A., Soci, C., Dee, D., Thépaut, J.-N. (2023): ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to present. Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS), DOI: 10.24381/cds.adbb2d47 (Accessed on 22-01-2024)

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Input files can be used to conduct simulations with other cloud models under similar conditions of cloud formation. They can also be used for teaching or training purposes in undergraduate and graduate courses.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

Yes

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/UCLALES-SALSA/UCLALES-SALSA>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

ISO 19115

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Metadata repository

<https://fmi.b2share.csc.fi/>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

climate science, aerosols, cloud, Climate Change

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Copernicus

METIS - Finnish Meteorological Institute Research Data repository

<https://fmi.b2share.csc.fi/>

Copernicus is the Earth observation component of the European Union's Space programme, looking at our planet and its environment to benefit all European citizens. It offers information services that draw from satellite Earth Observation and in-situ (non-space) data.

The European Commission manages the Programme. It is implemented in partnership with the Member States, the European Space Agency (ESA), the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), EU Agencies and Mercator Océan.

Vast amounts of global data from satellites and ground-based, airborne, and seaborne measurement systems provide information to help service providers, public authorities, and other international organisations improve European citizens' quality of life and beyond. The information services provided are free and openly accessible to users.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards

- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Uses non-proprietary formats
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Input data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

ACTRIS data for UCLALES-SALSA model validation

ACTRIS data used for UCLALES-SALSA model validation:

1. In-cloud droplet size distributions and ice size distributions.
2. Distribution of vertical wind from Doppler Lidar measurements
3. Distribution of radar velocity from cloud radar measurements

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Observational

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100 Gb

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To improve a product

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Observational data from ACTRIS research infrastructure:
<https://www.actris.eu/topical-centre/data-centre>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

Metadata exist

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

ACTRIS data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Details of ACTRIS quality control and assurance can be found here:

<https://www.actris.eu/catalogue-of-services/services>

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

EC-EARTH output

EC Earth output provides simulated physical and chemical properties of the Earth system. The data will be used in analyzing the interactions between aerosol, clouds, and climate.

The data is global 2D and 3D data of:

- chemical and physical properties of gas-phase and aerosol compounds
- cloud ice and liquid water contents, cloud and ice hydrometeor properties
- physical parameters of atmospheric dynamics, i.e. atmospheric circulation, temperature, and humidity
- properties of the Earth's surface

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Secondary data derived from raw EC-Earth output.

1.1.5 What is its format?

NetCDF

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Publication describing EC-Earth

<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-15-2973-2022>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners, climate research community.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

The FMI research data repository METIS is built together with EUDAT and is based on Datacite schema. In addition to the basic Datacite metadata, several specific institutional fields are added.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The FMI's metadata can be found in the national Finnish Fairdata services (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi>), OPENAIRE (<https://explore.openaire.eu>) and EOSC-portal (EOSC-portal.eu)

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

METIS

<https://fmi.b2share.csc.fi>

Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) research data repository METIS is provided by EUDAT and enables the institute data to be preserved, discovered, and accessed. FMI covers a wide range of research on weather, sea, climate and space. According to the FMI's Research Data policy, publicly funded research data must be made available to the widest possible audience (under CC BY license, at the minimum), as the best way to maximize the data impact but also to do justice to all the hard labor put into collecting, cleaning, and analyzing the data.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

FMI's research data repository is freely accessible to all researchers affiliated with the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI). This access is part of our institutional agreement with the repository, ensuring that FMI researchers can deposit, access, and utilize datasets without any individual subscription or specific arrangements.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

METIS provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

EC-EARTH output

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

FMI maintains a policy of retaining modeling data for a period of 10 years. Should external users continue to utilize the data extensively, this retention period may be prolonged.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period (if needed) is a maximum of 2 years from publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

EC-Earth is validated against in-situ observations, ground and satellite-based remote sensing. Data conforms the Climate Model Output Rewriter (CMOR) standards (see <https://cmor.llnl.gov/>)

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Anca Hienola (orcid:0000-0002-9612-1477)

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access

- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

UCLALES-SALSA outputs

Large eddy simulations on selected cloud cases for investigating the effects of aerosol-cloud interactions on cloud properties in cloud scale.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Time series of three dimensional data of macro and microphysical cloud properties, components of the radiation balance and meteorological variables

1.1.5 What is its format?

netcdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

3000000000

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information

- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study cloud processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

Tonttila J, Raatikainen T, Kokkola H, Ruuskanen A, & Romakkaniemi S. (2024, January, 23). UCLALES-SALSA/UCLALES-SALSA at <https://github.com/UCLALES-SALSA/UCLALES-SALSA/tree/master>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education

Project partners

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

The FMI research data repository METIS is built together with EUDAT and is based on Datacite schema. In addition to the basic Datacite metadata, several specific institutional fields are added.

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3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository

The FMI's metadata can be found in the national Finnish Fairdata services (<https://etsin.fairdata.fi>), OPENAIRE (<https://explore.openaire.eu>) and EOSC-portal ([EOSC-portal.eu](https://portal.eosc.eu))

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

climate science, climate change, cloud, aerosols

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

METIS

METIS - FMI's Research Data repository

METIS - FMI's Research Data repository <https://fmi.b2share.csc.fi>

Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) research data repository METIS is provided by EUDAT and enables the institute data to be preserved, discovered, and accessed. FMI covers a wide range of research on weather, sea, climate and space. According to the FMI's Research Data policy, publicly funded research data must be made available to the widest possible audience (under CC BY license, at the minimum), as the best way to maximize the data impact but also to do justice to all the hard labor put into collecting, cleaning, and analyzing the data.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

FMI's research data repository is freely accessible to all researchers affiliated with the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI). This access is part of our institutional agreement with the repository, ensuring that FMI researchers can deposit, access, and utilize datasets without any individual subscription or specific arrangements.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

METIS provides DOIs

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Time series of aerosol and cloud hydrometeor microphysics, radiation balance components and meteorological variables

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open, although a certain embargo period might be applied

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Throughout the project's duration, the dataset might be subject to an embargo of up to two years. During this period, access to the data will be restricted, but project partners can obtain access using specific tokens. Once the embargo period concludes and the project is completed, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

After the data become publicly accessible, it will not be possible to identify individuals who access the data. However, during the embargo period, access is controlled through tokens that are nominally issued to specific, selected partners.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

FMI maintains a policy of retaining modeling data for a period of 10 years. Should external users continue to utilize the data extensively, this retention period may be prolonged.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

The embargo period is 2 years from the moment of publication.

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Codebooks
- Data cleaning
- Analyses
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement
- Negative results sharing

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

Input data provenance will be linked in the metadata.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

Data conform to format specification

HArri to provide more details if needed

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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